

Excess Volumes of Mixtures containing *o*-Dichlorobenzene and Statistical Theory of Flory

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Excess volumes of *o*-dichlorobenzene + cyclohexane, + benzene + toluene, + *o*-xylene, + *m*-xylene, and + *p*-xylene have been measured at 303.15 and 308.15 K. The data have been analysed in the light of Flory theory.

THE application of revised^{1,2} two fluid model in conformational solutions theory to excess thermodynamic functions of simple fluid mixtures has lead to a considerable improvement in agreement between theory and experiment. The statistical theory of Flory^{3,4} was able to predict correctly the magnitude and sign of excess functions of mixtures of molecules differing in shape and size. This prompted us to determine the excess volumes of mixtures of *o*-dichlorobenzene with cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, and *p*-xylene and to analyse the data in the light of Flory theory.

Experimental

Cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, *p*-xylene, and *o*-dichlorobenzene (B. D. H.) were purified as described earlier^{5,6}.

Excess volumes of *o*-dichlorobenzene + cyclohexane, + benzene, + *o*-xylene, + *m*-xylene, + *p*-xylene, and + toluene were measured at 303.15 and 308.15 K by a dilatometric method⁷.

Results and Discussion

The excess volume data for these systems are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXCESS VOLUMES V^E OF MIXTURES CONTAINING *o*-DICHLOROBENZENE

x	$V^E / \text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E / \text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E / \text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E / \text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) cyclohexane at 303.15 K							
0.0896	0.081	0.2615	0.210	0.5386	0.282	0.7920	0.176
0.1102	0.098	0.3241	0.240	0.6074	0.261	0.8636	0.125
0.1637	0.147	0.3902	0.267	0.6649	0.247	0.9182	0.080
0.2132	0.170	0.4620	0.283	0.7164	0.221		
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) cyclohexane at 308.15 K							
0.0804	0.089	0.3886	0.270	0.6317	0.271	0.8402	0.159
0.1410	0.139	0.4758	0.297	0.7055	0.240	0.9062	0.104
0.2193	0.200	0.5542	0.292	0.7796	0.197	0.9305	0.080
0.2913	0.241						
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) benzene at 303.15 K							
0.0977	0.0218	0.3326	0.0628	0.6012	0.0699	0.7560	0.0520
0.1866	0.0385	0.3985	0.0686	0.6792	0.0629	0.8164	0.0386
0.2904	0.0553	0.4984	0.0733	0.7238	0.0536	0.9206	0.0184
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) benzene at 308.15 K							
0.0880	0.0154	0.3999	0.0553	0.5893	0.0585	0.7405	0.0384
0.1674	0.0269	0.4512	0.0612	0.6410	0.0518	0.8362	0.0261
0.2936	0.0463	0.5088	0.0640	0.6975	0.0469	0.9095	0.0154
0.3474	0.0532						
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) toluene at 303.15 K							
0.0764	-0.031	0.3996	-0.110	0.6966	-0.089	0.7725	-0.071
0.1997	-0.063	0.4917	-0.120	0.7607	-0.074	0.8799	-0.041
0.3196	-0.094	0.5999	-0.105				
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) toluene at 308.15 K							
0.1037	-0.040	0.2634	-0.089	0.4666	-0.125	0.6998	-0.095
0.1540	-0.056	0.3327	-0.104	0.5389	-0.122	0.8137	-0.065
0.2137	-0.075	0.3824	-0.115	0.5837	-0.116	0.9097	-0.035
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>o</i> -xylene at 303.15 K							
0.1086	-0.0281	0.3542	-0.0740	0.6430	-0.0793	0.8559	-0.0399
0.1800	-0.0468	0.4469	-0.0862	0.7186	-0.0717	0.8648	-0.0349
0.2598	-0.0607	0.5230	-0.0837	0.7702	-0.0568	0.9002	-0.0262

Cont.

x	$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	x	$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>o</i> -xylene at 308.15 K							
0.0802	-0.0212	0.3084	-0.0758	0.5614	-0.0919	0.8199	-0.0526
0.1410	-0.0408	0.3932	-0.0848	0.6554	-0.0846	0.8792	-0.0400
0.2199	-0.06022	0.4800	-0.0920	0.7406	-0.0720	0.9166	-0.0265
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>m</i> -xylene at 303.15 K							
0.0968	-0.048	0.3599	-0.110	0.6215	-0.122	0.8566	-0.066
0.1694	-0.068	0.4794	-0.133	0.7169	-0.104	0.8602	-0.057
0.2538	-0.095	0.5410	-0.134	0.7804	-0.085	0.9186	-0.037
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>m</i> -xylene at 308.15 K							
0.0802	-0.040	0.2737	-0.108	0.5406	-0.143	0.8012	-0.092
0.1341	-0.063	0.3668	-0.130	0.6232	-0.133	0.8604	-0.068
0.1886	-0.082	0.4493	-0.142	0.6998	-0.118	0.9088	-0.047
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>p</i> -xylene at 308.15 K							
0.0936	-0.048	0.3348	-0.129	0.5417	-0.144	0.8565	-0.068
0.1602	-0.078	0.5436	-0.148	0.6959	-0.114	0.8637	-0.056
0.2496	-0.106	0.4661	-0.145	0.7598	-0.096	0.9055	-0.040
x <i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + (1-x) <i>p</i> -xylene at 308.15K							
0.0807	-0.045	0.2796	-0.125	0.4901	-0.156	0.7813	-0.098
0.1388	-0.075	0.3445	-0.143	0.5997	-0.144	0.8426	-0.074
0.1898	-0.097	0.4200	-0.153	0.7041	-0.120	0.9113	-0.045

Procedure for computing excess volume V^E from Flory's theory: The excess volume V^E is related to the characteristic volume V^* for the components in the mixture by

$$V^E = \tilde{V}_{ca1}^E (x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^*) \dots \quad (1)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the mol fractions of the components in the mixture. The calculated excess reduced volume

$\tilde{V}_{ca1}^E$ is given by

$$\tilde{V}_{ca1}^E = \tilde{V}_0^{1/3} (4/3 - \tilde{V}_0^{1/3})^{-1} (\tilde{T} - \tilde{T}_0) \dots \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{V}_0$, $\tilde{T}$ and $\tilde{T}_0$ are the ideal reduced volume, the reduced temperature of the mixture and ideal

reduced temperature. The reduced temperature $\tilde{T}$ for the mixture is given by

$$\tilde{T} = \left[\frac{\phi_1 P_1^* \tilde{T}_1 + \phi_2 P_2^* \tilde{T}_2}{\phi_1 P_1^* + \phi_2 P_2^*} \right] \left[1 - \frac{\phi_1 \theta_2 \times_{12}}{\phi_1 P_1^* + \phi_2 P_2^*} \right]^{-1} \dots \quad (3)$$

where the terms have the same significance as given

by Flory^{3,4}. The reduced temperature $\tilde{T}$ of the mixture is dependent on the parameter $\theta_2 \times_{12}$ which can be evaluated from the knowledge of other excess functions of the system. Since other excess functions for these systems are not available, a departure has been made

from Flory's original method of evaluating $\tilde{T}$. The

reduced temperature $\tilde{T}$ of the mixture was obtained

from the relation $\tilde{T} = \phi_1 \tilde{T}_1 + \phi_2 \tilde{T}_2$ which is a reasonable approximation of equation (3). The values

of the parameters $\tilde{V}_0^{1/3}$, $\tilde{T}_0$, $\tilde{T}$ and $\tilde{V}_{ca1}^E$ are recorded in Table 2. V^E values thus computed are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2 - VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS OF FLORY THEORY

System	T/K	$\tilde{V}_0^{1/3}$	$\tilde{T}_0$	$\tilde{T}$	$\tilde{V}_{ca1}^E \times 10^{-4}$
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + cyclohexane benzene	303.15	1.0777	0.0576	0.0573	-1.916
	308.15	1.0800	0.0588	0.0585	-2.097
	303.15	1.0775	0.0575	0.0572	-2.242
	308.15	1.0794	0.0585	0.0578	-4.503
toluene	303.15	1.0753	0.0563	0.0561	-1.030
	308.15	1.0770	0.0572	0.0571	-1.049
<i>o</i> -xylene	303.15	1.0725	0.0548	0.0547	-0.375
	308.15	1.0737	0.0554	0.0554	-0.190
<i>m</i> -xylene	303.15	1.0725	0.0548	0.0547	-0.375
	308.15	1.0742	0.0557	0.0557	-0.255
<i>p</i> -xylene	303.15	1.0733	0.0552	0.0552	-0.568
	308.15	1.0750	0.0562	0.0561	-0.450

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTED V^E VALUES AT EQUIMOLAR COMPOSITIONS

System	T/K	$V^E / \text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	
		Experimental	Flory theory
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene + cyclohexane	303.15	0.280	-0.171
	308.15	0.294	-0.187
	303.15	0.072	-0.183
benzene	308.15	0.063	-0.367
	303.15	-0.112	-0.092
toluene	308.15	-0.121	-0.093
	303.15	-0.085	-0.036
<i>o</i> -xylene	308.15	-0.092	-0.018
	303.15	-0.134	-0.036
<i>m</i> -xylene	308.15	-0.141	-0.025
	303.15	-0.144	-0.055
<i>p</i> -xylene	308.15	-0.153	-0.043

The Flory's theory holds for mixtures of non-polar molecules but there is a good agreement between experimental and computed V^E values from Flory's theory for all the mixtures except *o*-dichlorobenzene + cyclohexane, and +benzene. The poor agreement in experimental V^E and computed V^E values in these two

mixtures is due to the assumption $T = \phi_1 \tilde{T}_1 + \phi_2 \tilde{T}_2$.

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